

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

УДК 811.111

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN INTEGRATED LEARNING WITH BIOLOGY

Kismetova G.,*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University***Zhaskairatova D.***Master's student of the philological faculty,
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7808645>*

Abstract

The upbringing of a well-rounded personality, capable of using the acquired knowledge in practice, is one of the important tasks of modern society. The article considers the integration of biology and English lessons, the advantages of the second language in learning. The necessity and urgency of holding integrated lessons that allow developing the learning process is grounded. The advantages of these lessons, including the motivation of students, the expansion of interdisciplinary links and the practical orientation of the lessons are noted.

Keywords: *English language, modern education, integrated lesson, biology, interdisciplinary connections, learning material.*

The current stage of society development requires new social demands on the educational system. The task is to form a highly intelligent and competitive personality of the student, who has a holistic view of the world and understands the relationship between processes and phenomena. Consequently, educational organizations face the task of combining knowledge obtained by students in different subjects into an integral system, which can be solved by integrating the subjects, which “becomes the principle of improving the content of education, the means of development of the educational process.” [4].

Thus, one of the relevant and promising areas of the educational process is the development and implementation of integrated lessons in which “topics are considered by means of two or more disciplines, carried out synthesis and systematization of knowledge, which provides the formation of students a holistic picture of the world, helps them learn relevant competencies.” [1]

The modern stage of development of the education system involves, among other things, updating the forms and content of teaching foreign languages. Recently, integrated lessons in a foreign language with other subjects of the curriculum is becoming increasingly popular. They allow you to create interdisciplinary links with school disciplines, both humanities and natural sciences cycles.

Interdisciplinary connections are a particularly significant factor in the formation of the content and structure of the academic subject in modern conditions. Interdisciplinary links provide an opportunity to link all the knowledge obtained in different subjects and background knowledge into a unified system. The lesson agrees with the modern point of view on the need not only to acquire practical skills, but also to develop the need to learn to acquire knowledge independently, to foster independent activity. [6]

There are great opportunities for the use of interdisciplinary links as a means of motivation of foreign

language speech activity in the conditions of secondary school with the proper organization of familiarization, training and application of language material, as well as timely control of the level of its mastering. These opportunities are inherent in the specificity of a foreign language as a school subject. Language is a means of expressing ideas about objective reality, properties, laws which are the subject of other disciplines, so language is subjectless. But being subjectless, it has many common points of contact with other school disciplines, that is, language is “polydisciplinary”. In turn, “polydisciplinarity” of a foreign language as a subject requires teachers to carry out interdisciplinary coordination in the process of teaching foreign language speech communication. [7]

When teachers work on mastering foreign language speech activities with the support of interdisciplinary links it is necessary to focus on the interests of students, take into account their individual characteristics and inclinations, which, naturally, will create the most favorable mode for the practical application of language as a means of communication. Because of this, interdisciplinary links are one of the effective means of motivating the learning process in a foreign language.

Integrated lessons should not be just one-time projects, because this method of learning subjects through English becomes effective only with an integrated approach in which knowledge of the subjects is gradually accumulated and language skills are improved, allowing students to apply their knowledge of English later when exploring and discussing new problems. Thus, in integrated lessons English becomes a means of acquiring subject knowledge rather than a goal of the learning process.

Integrated lessons in English and biology are worthwhile at different stages of school education. Already at the elementary level of education modern textbooks provide environmental pages where students get

acquainted with the world of plants and animals. Later they increase their knowledge, study the processes in nature, get acquainted with the specific professional vocabulary in English characteristic to a particular field of biology, which enables them to become more competent in the areas of their future professions. At the same time, motivation for learning both English and biology increases as students see their practical orientation.

The positive thing about additional English learning can be attributed to the fact that all learning develops. The study of grammar, vocabulary has a positive effect on memory, attention, and logic.

In the field of bilingualism, that is, when a person learns two languages, his native language and an additional foreign language, many studies have been and are being conducted. One of them is a study by the Department of Theoretical and Applied Linguistics at Cambridge University, where they showed that bilingualism in children is a positive phenomenon. Bilingual children have advantages in terms of social interaction, mental flexibility, and understanding of language structure. And bilinguals develop abstract thinking earlier, faster, better than monolinguals.

Psychologists Ellen Bialystock and Michelle Martin Rea studied bilingualism and concluded that bilinguals are superior to monolinguals in performing tasks with mixed visual and verbal information. Their abilities develop more actively when the brain triggers higher cognitive processes for problem solving, memory development, and thought activity.

An integrated lesson of English and biology “can be conducted either by one English teacher or together with a biology teacher, in which case the latter presents material in the native language and summarizes the knowledge that children already have in this subject.” [2]

It is important to note that today's educational system is constantly evolving and moving only forward. This is evidenced by the university education, especially the sphere of pedagogy. Recently, in the universities of the Republic of Kazakhstan a new direction was opened, where specially prepared specialists are trained, i.e. teachers, who can teach their basic subjects of natural and mathematical cycle, such as biology, physics, etc. in English. For these professionals, the main subject of study is the subjects of the natural-mathematical cycle, and the secondary subject is English. At the end of training in this specialty, the graduate receives a diploma, where in the appendix to the diploma it is noted that this is a specialist who can teach the subject not only in the native language, but also in English. In my opinion, this facilitates the organization of integrated teaching of the subject and language in modern schools, as it does not require combining several specialists.

Preparation for the integrated English and biology lessons is carried out according to the following plan:

- - a preliminary study and analysis of a biology topic that will integrate English;
- - selection of materials on the topic of study in English, taking into account the school curriculum, age and level of English proficiency of students;

- - composing questions, assignments, and interactive exercises that develop both subject matter and language skills;

- - highlighting the necessary active vocabulary.

When selecting material for integrated lessons, it should be remembered that in the process of work the students should develop all kinds of speech activity. Therefore it is important to prepare for the lessons both text material and audio or video files. The latter allow for a visual demonstration of certain processes and phenomena. When introducing and consolidating new vocabulary, various exercises can be used, for example, signing elements on pictures, filling in tables, arranging words by categories, etc.

Next, we work with terminology and definitions. When introducing the topic, it is advisable to make explanations in the native language, since the material in biology, along with the language, is new to the students. To consolidate and check you can use small tests, most often these are multiple choice tests. You can give a definition and from the proposed, placed in a scattering of letters need to write the term. On the Internet you can find interactive exercises or create them yourself.

Working with texts, it is necessary, first of all, to understand that in them students are faced with scientific material, which may cause them certain difficulties. Therefore, at the so-called pre-textual stage, it is necessary to work on the vocabulary and repeat the grammar that are found in the text. The next stage, direct familiarity with the text, involves a variety of exercises such as confirming the correctness or falsity of statements, finding matches, answering questions, etc. And finally, at the post-text stage it is necessary to check how much the students have understood the content of the topic. For this purpose it is necessary to analyze the basic concepts once again, it is possible to perform a number of exercises, such as agree with the statement or refute it, characterize or prove something, etc. Similarly, work is done with audio recordings and films.

The structure of integrated lessons differs from conventional lessons in the following ways:

- - the ultimate clarity, compactness, and conciseness of the training material;
- - the logical interdependence, the interdependence of the material of the subjects being integrated at each stage of the lesson;
- - a large informative capacity of educational material used in the lesson.

Thus, English becomes an excellent platform for building students' knowledge related to biology. Integrated lessons allow you to effectively combine the two subjects, increasing the motivation of students to learn both biology and to improve their language skills. Often, the knowledge and teachings gained in such lessons are later applied in other subjects and in real life.

References:

1. Vavilova L. N. Integrated lesson: features, preparation, conducting. [Electronic resource]: CyberLeninka - URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/integrirrovanny-urok-osobnosti-podgotovka-provedenie>
2. Integrated Lesson: How to Combine English with Other Subjects? [Electronic resource]: skyteach - URL: <https://skyteach.ru/2021/02/17/kak-integrirrovat-anglijskij-yazyk-s-drugimi-predmetami/>
3. Interdisciplinary integration in the learning process in the lessons of a foreign language and biology. [Electronic resource]: skyteach - URL: <https://slovo.mosmetod.ru/2015/10/06/beljaeva-e-n-azarenkova-e-m-mezhpredmetn/>
4. Teremov A.V. Integrative tendencies in natural-science and humanities education of schoolchildren: Ph: 13.00.01/A.V. Teremov: GOU VPO MPGU. M: 2007.
5. Turchinova G.V. Formation of professional skills of teaching biology in English // Scientific notes // Series: Pedagogical and Historical Sciences. - K.: Publishing center of National Pedagogical University named after Dragomanov, 2005. - Vol. LVIII. - pp. 156-164.
6. Vorobyeva, L.F. Interdisciplinary links in the lessons of the German language, Foreign languages at school - №1 - 1989. - 9 p.
7. Zverev I.D., Maximova V.N. Interdisciplinary links in the modern school: textbook / I.D. Zverev, V.N. Maximova. - M.: Pedagogics, 1987, - 412 pp.
8. Kolyagin, Y.M., Alekseenko, O.L. Integration of school education, Nachalnaya shkola - No. 9 - 1990. - 32 p.
9. Maximova V.N., Gruzdeva N.V. Interdisciplinary links in education: a training manual / V.N. Maximova, N.V. Gruzdeva. - M.: Prosveshchenie, 1987, - 214 p.